

Instruction Following Using Vision and Natural Language

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Abstract

Embodied instruction following is a complex task that involves an agent inferring a series of basic actions from complex language and visual inputs in order to achieve a desired state in the environment. To address this challenge, a benchmark called Action Learning From Realistic Environments and Directives (ALFRED) has been introduced. ALFRED presents a collection of detailed natural language instructions that guide the agent in accomplishing subgoals that collectively contribute to achieving a higher-level objective. ALFRED dataset [1] contains roughly 25K language annotations of both high-level goals and low-level step-by-step instructions for various long-horizon and compositional tasks set in the AI2-THOR simulator [2]. Key challenges for this task include localizing target locations and navigating to them through visual inputs and grounding language instructions to the visual appearance of objects. In this project, we have provided results for an end-to-end approach that are better than the baselines in all the metrics but cannot beat the current state-of-the-art [3]. We have also worked on modular approaches to solve such tasks. We modify the deterministic policy in the existing modular approach FILM [4] and improved the performance by 5.82%. We also considered creating semantic maps [5] by matching photos to descriptions of item purposes in natural language that allows us to transform the navigation description of the goal into a list of open-vocabulary navigational objectives that are immediately localized on the map.

1 INTRODUCTION

For in-home robots to become a reality, the underlying problem of vision, language, and robotics to be solved. Embodied Instruction Following (EIF) is a problem where an agent must complete a task by following a human teacher’s language instructions. The language instructions may require the agent to navigate through a space, and manipulate objects in the space. Action Learning From Realistic Environments and Directives (ALFRED) is a recently introduced benchmark dataset for embodied task learning, providing human-written natural language instructions for an agent to perform tasks in a virtual environment with continuous navigation. The agent is required to execute sequences of sub-tasks that entail both navigation and interaction actions from a language instruction, given at each time step an egocentric view of the environment and a choice of choosing one action from five navigation actions (RotateRight, RotateLeft, MoveAhead, LookUp, LookDown) or seven object interaction actions (PickupObject, PutObject, OpenOb-

ject, CloseObject, ToggleObjectOn, ToggleObjectOff, SliceObject). The interaction actions must be accompanied by an image mask specifying the location of the interaction target in the agent’s view. An episode ends when the task is finished, 1000 steps are taken, or 10 bad interactions (e.g., collisions, interacting with non-interactive objects) occur.

The data set in ALFRED is given in the form of expert trajectories. For each time step in each goal, we are given the action taken by the expert and the corresponding egocentric view of the environment. For each example trajectory, the subgoals have been annotated by at least 3 different annotators. The tasks are of indoor household nature held in 120 indoor scenes in AI2-THOR 2.0 simulator [2]. These demonstrations involve partial observability, long action horizons, under-specified natural language, and irreversible actions. ALFRED includes 25,743 English language directives describing 8,055 expert demonstrations averaging 50 steps each, resulting in 428,322 image-action pairs.

Figure 1: A sample episode in ALFRED. Texts in white boxes correspond to the low-level instructions.

2 Literature Survey

We have surveyed a number of papers based on the approaches to solving the problem. These approaches can be broadly classified as End to End or Modular approaches. End to End approaches perform supervised learning using expert trajectories by taking the language features (low-level instructions along with a high-level goal), visual features (Agent’s egocentric view), and past low-level action sequence as input and predicting the subsequent low-level action and an interaction mask in case of an interaction action and the parameters of the model are learned using imitation learning on expert trajectories. Whereas, modular approaches focus on a systematic approach to the navigation tasks. These are generally accompanied by building up a plan for the navigation task followed by an execution phase where the plan is executed in the given environment. Based on the surveys and recent advancements, it is evident that modular approaches yield better performance results than end-to-end approaches because they are explainable, easy to debug, and better capture the long horizon navigation tasks.

2.1 End to End Approaches

Shridhar et. al. [1] Authors of ALFRED Dataset model the interactive agent with a CNN-LSTM

sequence-to-sequence (SEQ2SEQ) architecture. A CNN encodes the visual input, a bidirectional LSTM generates a representation of the language input, and a decoder LSTM infers a sequence of low-level actions while attending to the encoded language. Action selection is trained using cross-entropy with the expert action. The interaction masks are learned end-to-end in a supervised manner based on ground-truth object segmentation using binary cross-entropy loss.

Kim et. al. [6] proposes ViLT - Vision-and-Language Transformer that consists of transformer encoder (stacked blocks that include a multiheaded self-attention (MSA) layer and an MLP layer). The text and image embeddings are summed with their corresponding modal-type embedding vectors and are concatenated into a combined sequence which is iteratively updated through transformer layers up until the final contextualized sequence is obtained. The embeddings thus obtained are used in the downstream task of predicting the next action and the interaction mask in ALFRED.

Guhur et. al. [7] proposes a large-scale and diverse in-domain Vision-and-language navigation (VLN) dataset that uses real-life images from online rental marketplaces and proposes automatic strategies to generate millions of VLN path-instruction pairs based on images and image-caption pairs from hundreds of thousands of listings from the images. This dataset obtained is then used to train their Airbert model for Room-to-Room navigation and Remote Referring Expression (REVERIE) benchmarks.

Yang et. al. [8] proposes to use Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) for incorporating the prior knowledge into a deep reinforcement learning Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic framework (A3C model) in AI2-THOR framework. They show that semantic prior knowledge can significantly improve navigation performance. The model learns a policy network that decides an action based on the visual features of the current state, the semantic target category feature, and the features extracted from the knowledge graph.

Kwon et. al. [9] propose a graph-structured memory for visual navigation, called visual graph memory (VGM), which consists of unsupervised image representations obtained from navigation history. VGM is constructed incrementally based on the similarities among the unsupervised representations of observed images, and these representations are learned from an unlabeled image dataset. Using the VGM, the agent can embed its navigation history and other useful task-related information on image-goal navigation tasks.

2.2 Modular Approaches

Storks et. al. [10] modified the model in [1] by executing only one sub-goal at a time, augmenting additional visual observation at each time step, and adding an object detection module [11] to the agent’s visual observations. Their architecture uses a variation of BERT [12] that encodes the panoramic bounding box at each time step along with the current and the next sub-goal instruction to produce an embedding for the current time step which is then used to estimate the next action the agent must take.

Min et. al. [4] introduced the FILM model (Following Instructions in Language with Modular methods) that consists of various modular components. Language Processing Module processes language instructions into a structured form. Semantic Mapping Module converts agent’s egocentric vision to a semantic map [13]. The deterministic Policy Module outputs the subsequent action/interaction that the agent must take.

Inoue and Ohashi [3] extended the work done by [4] without requiring any additional data. Their model FILM++ uses Large Language Model (LLM) Prompting for a deployment-friendly semantic search module. LLM Prompting [14] exploits mask filling capability of off-the-shelf LLMs by masking out the information to be needed. For example, if one wants to know the landmark for an apple, the input can be given to LLMs as “Apple is found at [MASK]”. LLM then fills the mask with the most likely answer, which in this case could be “refrigerator”. Authors have used prompting to extract the likelihood of object pairs occurring together, which is then used to guide the object search. FILM++ obtains the current State-of-the-Art results achieving an accuracy of 45.72% on unseen environments outperforming the previous state-of-the-art by 10.3%.

Huang et. al. [5] proposed VLMaps, combining 3D reconstruction with pretrained visuallanguage characteristics. They do so by computing dense pixel-level embeddings from an existing visual language model LSeg [15] (over the robot’s video stream) and back project them onto the environment’s 3D surface (collected from depth data utilised for reconstruction using visual odometry). LSeg [16] is a language-driven semantic segmentation model that divides RGB pictures into a collection of free-form language categories. The embedding of each pixel in the picture is mapped by the LSeg visual encoder to be in the CLIP feature

space [17]. They combine the LSeg pixel embeddings with the appropriate 3D map positions without explicit manual segmentation only requiring access to odometry (use of data from motion sensors to estimate the change in position over time) and helps in the creation of semantic maps from collections of RGB-D photos.

Chen et. al. [18] proposed similar representation for EIF task through NLMap, an open-vocabulary and queryable scene representation framework that collects and integrates the contextual information of a scene such that LLM planners can see and query available objects in the scene that aids in generating a context-conditioned plan. Their model NLMap + SayCan first executes an exploration phase wherein the agent explores the given scene; during this exploration, their model observes each Region of Interest (RoI) and encodes it to create image embeddings using CLIP [17] and ViLD [19]. These embeddings are then integrated using NLMap which allows for context-based planning. They benchmark their model on a real-world kitchen a real-world kitchen, demonstrating its ability to complete 55 tasks with a 61.8% success rate. Notably, 35 of these tasks were not completed by current state-of-the-art planners at that time without access to NLMap.

3 Proposed Approach

We looked at both approaches (End-to-End and Modular) for the ALFRED challenge. We also analyze how our proposed model generalizes for other EIF tasks, including RGB-D images from real-life environments. Our end-to-end approach is based on ViLT (Vision-and-Language Transformer) [6] and Airbert [7] which are then fine-tuned for the downstream task in ALFRED dataset. For modular approach, we analyze how FILM [4], VLMaps [5], and NLMaps [18] work for ALFRED dataset and further modify the FILM model and improved the performance by 8.82%.

3.1 End-to-End Approach

3.1.1 ViLT + Collision Detection

ViLT encodes goal instruction, step-by-step instructions, and the previous 8 actions as a part of language input and the current front, left and right egocentric image observation of the agent as an image section. The embedding thus obtained is used in a downstream task to predict the next action, the target object, and the receptacle object.

Formally, the language input text $t \in R^{L \times |V|}$ is embedded to $\bar{t} \in R^{L \times H}$ with a word embedding matrix $T \in R^{|V| \times H}$ and a position embedding matrix $T^{pos} \in R^{(L+1) \times H}$ where L is the length of input, $|V|$ is the size of input vocabulary and H is the embedding dimension. The input image $I \in R^{C \times H \times W}$ is sliced into 3 patches (front, left, and right) and flattened followed by linear projection and position embedding $V^{pos} \in R^{(N+1) \times H}$ to get the image embedding $\bar{v} \in R^{N \times H}$ where $N = HW/P^2$, (P, P) being the patch resolution.

The text and image embeddings are then concatenated into a combined sequence z^0 . The context vector z is then iteratively updated through D -depth transformer layers to get the final contextualized sequence z^D .

The output z^D is passed through 3 different fully connected dense layers each of size 2048 and then to the output layers to predict the next low-level action, target object, and the receptacle object. Dropout of 0.1 is applied to the fully connected layers, and ReLU activation is applied on the hidden layers. The output layer is followed by a softmax layer.

Figure 2: Model Architecture for ViLT+CD. For Airbert+CD, we replace ViLT model by Airbert model.

For all experiments, we tokenized the language input using a BERT tokenizer, and then passed it through the BERT Embedding Layer. The output of the BERT Embedding Layer forms the input for the ViLT model. We use the [SEP] token to separate the three different input types in the text (High-level instruction, Low-level step-by-step instructions, and past action history). We use weights from ViLT pre-trained on ImageNet, Hidden size $H = 768$, depth of transformer layer $D = 12$, patch size $P = 32$, and the number of attention heads = 12.

For object detection, we used a MaskRCNN model

pre-trained on the ALFRED dataset [20]. Object detection is useful to check whether the target object is in the agent’s view. The bounding box predicted by MaskRCNN is needed in case of interaction/manipulation actions.

3.1.2 Airbert + Collision Detection

Airbert has a structure similar to ViLBERT [21] which is a multi-modal transformer extended from BERT [12]. ViLBERT is used to learn visual-linguistic representations from images and text usually in the form of image-caption pairs.

Formally, given an image text pair (V, C) , the image is encoded as region features $[v_1, \dots, v_\nu]$ using a pre-trained model Faster R-CNN [22], and textual embeddings are obtained as a series of tokens: $[[CLS], w_1, \dots, w_T, [SEP]]$, where [CLS] and [SEP] are special tokens added to the text. The visual and text inputs to Airbert are

$$X_V = [[IMG], v_1^1, \dots, v_1^1, \dots, [IMG], v_1^K, \dots, v_K^K],$$

$$X_C = [[CLS], w_1^1, \dots, w_{T_1}^1, \dots, w_1^K, \dots, w_{T_K}^K, [SEP]],$$

for each image and caption $\{(V_k, C_k)\}_{k=1}^K$, V_k is represented using visual regions v_i^k , and C_k as word tokens w_t^k , [IMG] token is used to distinguish image features from different regions.

The input is then iteratively updated similar to ViLT architecture and is then used in the downstream task of predicting the next action, the target object, and the receptacle object.

3.2 Modular Approach

3.2.1 Improvements on FILM Model [4]

There are three essential components to our suggested approach. Navigation through visual observation, active search and task change, and semantic segmentation error fixes for ALFRED dataset.

The existing FILM model contains several modular components:

Language Processing Module processes the high-level instructions into a sequence of well-structured sub-tasks. It comprises of two BERT [23] submodules: BERT type classification and BERT argument classification. BERT type classification predicts the type of the current high-level instruction from one of the seven task categories. BERT argument classification takes the instruction and the predicted type from BERT

Figure 3: FILM Method Overview. Image taken from [4]

Semantic Mapping Module takes the current egocentric RGB image from the agent and processes it into depth map and instance segmentation map using MaskRCNN [20]. The depth observation is then converted to a point cloud, where each point is connected to the projected semantic categories. Each point in the point cloud is then projected in 3D space using differentiable geometric computations to get the voxel representation. The voxel representation is then converted to the semantic map which gets updated locally and aggregates over time. *Semantic Search Policy* generates a 2D distribution of potential locations for small subgoal objects using a semantic map. Discovering small objects is challenging due to their size, limited field of view, and limitations in semantic segmentation. The policy predicts search locations based on the arrangement of larger objects, without relying on expert trajectories for learning. Based on the observed spatial arrangement of larger objects, the semantic search policy aims to predict where to look for small objects, which is learned agnostic to the expert trajectories.

The three main elements of our suggested strategy are: integrating visual observations while navigating, actively looking for and modifying subtasks similar to [3], and resolving problems in semantic segmentation.

Modifying Visual Observations

Visual observations are used during navigation to reduce reliance on the semantic map. The search goal coordinates are updated to the current position if the goal object is found inside the current visual observation frame. This makes sure the agent does not miss the objective item that is right in front of it. By leveraging visual observations during navigation, this approach dynamically adjusts the search goal coordinates to the agent’s current location, effectively

preventing it from overlooking the goal object in its egocentric vision.

Modifying Subtasks

Similar to the work done in [3] and [4], the language input is transformed into structured templates of subtasks. A comparable “type template” with empty arguments is used to compare the expected “type” of the instruction to it. For instance, if the instruction is labelled “pick place,” the template “(Obj, PickUp), (Recep, PutObject)” is matched with the instruction. Additional subtasks such as “(Knife, PickUp), (Obj, Slice), (Recep, PutObject)” are added at the start of the template if the argument classification reveals that the “sliced” argument is true. A list of subtasks is created for the current episode to fill the template.

A new subtask is added to the list for opening the appropriate receptacle in situations where the agent is unable to locate the required objective object in the environment. For instance, the subtask (Fridge, “OpenObject”) is present in the subtask list if the goal object is not found despite being anticipated to be inside the “Fridge”.

Modifying Semantic Segmentation

The execution of interaction actions becomes challenging when the mask and action need to be anticipated simultaneously. This is often due to inaccurate predictions from MaskRCNN as shown in Fig. -. Moreover, the pre-trained MaskRCNN has trouble predicting the “type” of an object, specifically whether the object is slice-able or toggle-able, making any distinction between them irrelevant in the context of subtasks. Thus, we removed the “slice-able” and “toggle-able” objects from the subtasks template and treat the slice-able and non-slice-able objects as one (similarly with toggle-able objects).

Fig. 4: **LEFT.** An instance where the bounding boxes and object classes are appropriately represented by Mask-RCNN. **RIGHT.** An instance where the object “tomato” gets incorrectly labeled as “sports ball” and refrigerator object is incorrectly classified as a “book” with an incorrect bounding box.

Figure 5: Our proposed modification for FILM Model.

Moreover, when the agent reaches the final goal location, but the MaskRCNN cannot locate the correct goal mask, the agent keeps on turning left or right, which leads to the agent getting caught in a cycle of camera rotations. We realize that this occurs when the desired object is only partially visible within the current visual observation frame, irrespective of the camera rotation. Hence, we made adjustments to the algorithm by incorporating a movement strategy to reposition the agent behind the goal object in order to capture the entire scene, in case a camera rotation loop occurs.

3.2.2 Visual Language Maps for ALFRED

In previous sections, we used pre-trained off-the-shelf models for fine-tuning for ALFRED scenes. But for an agent to perform navigation in any new environment, we do not necessarily require and/or have sufficient data for training the models. To address this issue, we looked at VLMs [5], which combines pre-trained visual-language features with a 3D reconstruction of the physical environment. This integration allows spatial map representation to be constructed autonomously using RGB-D images from the agent. VLMs enables natural language indexing of the map without requiring additional labeled data and can therefore be used in the settings where the navigation task is open-vocabulary (e.g. “in between two

objects” or “revolve around the object 3 times”).

We used VLMs to enable open-vocabulary indexing in ALFRED scenes. For this, we extracted RGB and depth features from the current visual observation along with the camera pose and feed it to VLM Semantic Map Creation Module. This gives us the semantic map for the current trajectory which is then used to guide the final goal using landmark indexing using CLIP text encoder [24]. The semantic maps obtained and open vocabulary indexing results are shown in the results section.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 ALFRED Benchmark

ALFRED benchmark contains 820 validation seen episodes, 821 validation unseen episodes, 1533 test seen episodes, and 1529 test unseen episodes. Here seen/unseen signifies seen/unseen environments. This split according to environments examines how well a model generalizes to any new arbitrary environment with unseen object class variations. For each demonstration regarding a high-level goal, the subgoals have been annotated by at least 3 different human annotators. Environments in ALFRED consist of 30 rooms each of Kitchen, Living Room, Bathroom, and Bedroom. There are 7 different tasks in ALFRED pa-

parameterized by 84 object classes out of which 20 are receptacle classes (Ex. Sink, Countertop, Refrigerator, etc.). These tasks are: Pick and Place (Put an item in a receptacle), Stack and Place (Stack item1 in item2 and put in a receptacle), Pick Two and Place (Put item1 and item2 in a receptacle), Clean and Place (clean item1 using item2 and place in a receptacle), Heat and Place (Heat item and place in a receptacle), Cool and Place (Cool item and place in a receptacle), Examine in Light (examine item in the light source). An agent can choose to take an action from five navigation actions (RotateRight, RotateLeft, MoveAhead, LookUp, LookDown) or from seven object interaction actions (PickupObject, PutObject, OpenObject, CloseObject, ToggleObjectOn, ToggleObjectOff, SliceObject). State changes of some objects are irreversible (Ex., An object once sliced cannot be unsliced) and each object permits only a few state changes among Openable, Movable, Toggleable, Heatable, Coolable, and Slice-able.

4.2 Evaluation Metrics

ALFRED allows for both full task and task-goal condition completion. A full task is complete only when all of its goal conditions have been completed.

Task Success. Each episode in ALFRED is parameterized by a task that needs to be performed. Task Success is a binary value defined as 1 if the position of all the objects and the state changes correctly corresponds to the task goal conditions at the end of the episode, and 0 otherwise. Example for the task: “Examine the keys under the light of the table lamp”, task success is 1 if at the end of the episode, the table lamp is in ON condition, and the agent has the keys in its hand and is standing within 1.5 meters from the table lamp.

Goal-Condition Success. It is defined as the ratio of total goal conditions completed by the agent at the end of an episode to those necessarily required to be finished in order to complete the task. For example, in the previous “Examine in Light task”, if the agent examined the key without toggling ON the table lamp, its goal-condition success score will be $3/4 = 75\%$. ALFRED has 2.55 goal conditions per task on average. The final score is calculated as the average goal-condition success of each episode.

Path Weighted Metrics. Demonstrations in ALFRED are optimal: the agent avoids exploration, uses the shortest path, and completes the task in minimal steps. The path-weighted metrics is designed to penalize the agent for taking more steps to complete the task in hand. Formally, the path weighted score p_s for

any metric s is given as:

$$p_s = s \times \frac{L^*}{\max(L^*, \hat{L})} \quad (1)$$

where \hat{L} is the agent’s number of actions in the episode, and L^* is the number of actions in the expert demonstration. An agent that takes twice the steps to complete the task as compared to an expert receives half credit for any metric s .

Sub Goal Evaluation. The agent must complete the sub-goal conditioned on the language derivative and the agent’s visual observation. There are 8 fundamental high-level subgoals: GoTo (navigate to some place), Pickup (pick up a movable object), Put (place object that has been picked up in a receptacle), Cool (cool an object), Heat (heat up an object), Clean (remove objects on a surface), Slice (cut an object) and Toggle (toggle an object). For the task “Examine the keys under the light of the table lamp”, we can evaluate the sub-goal GoTo when the agent successfully navigates to the keys and table lamp. A task in ALFRED contains 7.5 subgoals on average.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 End-to-End Approach

The models in this approach (ViLT+CD and AirBERT+CD) were trained for roughly 160,000 iterations using AdamW optimizer [26] with a batch size of 32 and learning rate of 10^{-4} . The model is trained on 4 epochs, dividing files into folds of 25 each (each fold containing roughly 480 trajectories), over the training dataset using NVIDIA’s RTX3060 GPU.

Seq2Seq architecture [1] is taken as a baseline, HiTUT [25], the state-of-the-art model for an end-to-end approach, is used as a comparison. Also utilized as a point of comparison is the most recent state-of-the-art model FILM++ [3], which takes a modular approach. These models are compared against our two approaches ViLT+CD and Airbert+CD.

In Table 1, we have provided task Success, and goal-Condition results for different data splits. Table 2 displays a model’s capacity to complete the subsequent sub-goal based on the previous expert sequence. We note that from our proposed models, version 2 (Airbert+CD) performs marginally better than version 1 (ViLT + CD).

Models	Validation				Test			
	Seen		Unseen		Seen		Unseen	
	Task	GC	Task	GC	Task	GC	Task	GC
Seq2Seq [1]	2.4	9.4	0.1	6.8	2.1	7.4	0.5	7.1
HiTUT [25]	25.24	34.85	12.44	23.71	21.27	29.97	13.87	20.31
ViLT+CD	5.6	15.1	2.4	11.7	3.65	10.6	1.46	8.4
Airbert+CD	8.2	19.1	1.9	11.1	4.2	15.8	1.6	6.9
FILM++ [3]	53.23	63.43	25.81	30.72	53.23	63.43	45.72	58.76
Human Evaluation	-	-	-	-	-	-	91	94.5

Table 1: **Task and Goal-Condition Success.** All values are in percentages.

	Model	GoTo	Pickup	Put	Cool	Heat	Clean	Slice	Toggle	Avg
<i>Seen</i>	Seq2Seq [1]	51	32	81	88	85	81	25	100	70
	HiTUT [25]	79	81	77	95	100	83	81	97	88
	ViLT+CD	44	62	68	71	90	22	77	77	73
	Airbert+CD	44	58	74	81	95	12	70	61	71
<i>Unseen</i>	Seq2Seq [1]	17	21	46	92	89	57	12	32	50
	HiTUT [25]	81	71	69	94	97	91	78	58	81
	ViLT+CD	30	52	53	75	89	86	60	84	67
	Airbert+CD	41	58	74	90	95	66	48	91	71

Table 2: **Evaluations by path weighted sub-goal success in Validation set.** All values are in percentages.

Models	Valid Seen				Valid Unseen			
	GC_p	GC	SR_p	SR	GC_p	GC	SR_p	SR
FILM [4]	-	37.2	-	24.63	-	32.4	-	20.1
Our Approach	11.67	34.5	7.45	25.71	6.27	29.7	8.3	20.3

Table 3: **Goal-Condition Success on Validation split.** GC_p indicates path weighted goal-condition success and SR_p indicates path-weighted task-success rate. All values are in percentages.

Task Type	Valid Seen				Valid Unseen			
	FILM		Our Approach		FILM		Our Approach	
	GC	SR	GC	SR	GC	SR	GC	SR
Examine	50.0	64.1	51.6	43.2	43.6	30.1	44.9	30.1
Pick & Place	27.4	28.2	27.8	28.5	16.7	15.3	11.2	10.0
Stack & Place	24.4	11.2	23.0	10.6	9.0	1.9	10.1	2.4
Clean & Place	57.6	44.0	55.7	41.0	49.1	33.7	45.4	33.1
Cool & Place	26.6	12.6	30.2	21.7	27.1	14.8	27.1	15.6
Heat & Place	40.1	23.0	33.7	23.4	37.7	24.0	33.0	22.5
Pick2 & Place	40.7	23.5	32.1	18.4	29.4	12.3	11.5	6.3

Table 4: **Task Success on Validation split.** All values are in percentages.

Fig. 6: **LEFT.** Different Visual Observations for Current RGB Frame in ALFRED. **RIGHT.** Comparison of the object masks generated by VLMaps and LM-Nav for the object type “chair” for the current visual observation.

4.3.2 Modular Approach

We compared our model against the original FILM [4]. The results are shown in Table 3 and 4. Table 3 shows that our approach exhibits slightly superior performance compared to the original method on both Valid Seen and Unseen scenarios, with an improved success rate (SR) of 0.74% and 0.36% respectively. Although, there is a reduction of 1.42% in the goal-conditioned success rate (GC) on the Valid Seen split and a decrease of 0.86% on the Valid Unseen split. Table 4 shows a significant improvement in performance (8.82%) particularly for the task type “Cool and Place”. This indicates that our modification in subtasks helps in improving this task type because of the fact that some of the objects are present in the “refrigerator” which requires additional (Fridge, “OpenObject”) subtask. This greatly increases the SR.

For VLMaps, we worked on AI2THOR simulator because of its compatibility with different agent types such as drones and LocoBot. We compared the results with LM-Nav [27] which creates a network where visual observations of the surroundings are kept as nodes, and edges are used to express the proximity between images. By fusing GPT-3 and CLIP, the system processes user commands, extracts landmarks, and creates graph navigation plans to move towards the goal. The AI2Thor rendered scene images and the results obtained from VLMaps and LMNav are shown in Figure 6.

Our observation indicates that VLMaps consistently outperforms the baseline model LM-Nav. LM-Nav, exhibits weak performance due to its limited ability

to navigate only to locations represented by images stored in graph nodes. In order to gain deeper insights into the map-based approaches, we analyze and compare the object masks generated by VLMaps and LM-Nav for the object type “chair” for the current visual observation. The masks generated by LM-Nav contain a significant number of false positive predictions. Since the planning process relies on reaching the nearest masked target area, these inaccurate predictions result in planning paths towards incorrect goals. In contrast, the predictions obtained with VLMaps exhibit less noise, leading to higher success rates in object navigation.

5 Conclusion

We suggested two end-to-end approaches and modified the FILM’s modular approach to solve the ALFRED Challenge. We also looked at VLMaps to obtain natural language indexing of the map without requiring additional labeled data.

For end-to-end approach, both our model outperform the baseline model [1]; however, in comparison to the most recent model, they fall far short. Although we see comparable results in path weighted sub-goal success rates (Table 2), but some sub-goals are considerably harder than others. Simpler sub-goals like **Cool** and **Heat** do not require additional object knowledge. For example, **Cool** sub-goal is associated only with the object “refrigerator” and the model learns to associate cooling things with “refrigerator” object irrespective of the object in-hand. Overall, although outperforming the baseline, our model still needs to account for

the implicit hierarchy among the sub-objectives to improve performance.

For modular approach, we looked at FILM model [4] and proposed changes to its pipeline. Our modified model improved success rate (SR) of 0.74% and 0.36% respectively for valid seen and unseen environments. Our model also showed a significant improvement in performance (8.82%) for the task type “Cool and Place” indicating that our proposed improvement works well.

We also looked at VLMaps [5] to enable open-vocabulary indexing in ALFRED scenes. VLMaps outperformed the baseline model LM-Nav [27] due to LM-Nav containing significant number of false positive predictions, while in contrast, the predictions obtained with VLMaps received less noise, leading to higher success rates in object navigation.

6 Future Work

Although recent advancements in the ALFRED challenge demonstrate improved performance when adopting modular strategies, one can also try Reinforcement Learning methods like Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning (HRL) which decomposes a long-horizon task into a hierarchy of sub-problems such that a higher-level policy learns to perform the task by choosing optimal sub-tasks as the higher-level actions. One can also try modifying Mask-RCNN and Fast-RCNN models for semantic segmentation which use CNN as their backbone. The semantic mapping module does not take care of dynamic objects which can be displaced in the environment, so one can also try building up dynamic semantic mapping modules to further guide the navigation. All our models fail to resolve object ambiguities when there are multiple objects cluttered around the same observation space, so one can design algorithms in case of distinguishing the target object from a clutter of objects.

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